

Original Article

Smart control of heavy metal adsorption onto LDC wastes for Industry 4.0 applications

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ABSTRACT

Due to the complexity and the need for automation in adsorption systems, this study develops a decision-making model using 20 Machine Learning Algorithms (MLAs), Response Surface Methodology (RSM), and lab tests. Inputs include pH, metal type, concentration, adsorbent mass, and time; output is removal percentage for process control. The best-performing models (Tree Random Forest: TRF, lazy Instance-Based K: IBK, and Function Multilayer Perceptron: FMLP) achieve high accuracy for prediction of Removal Percentage (RP) of heavy metals with >0.92 correlation coefficient and >0.8 recall/precision indicators. As a novelty of this study, a decision-making model for the heavy metal adsorption process onto waste materials is developed for the first time using the Knowledge Flow (KF) platform in WEKA software, incorporating real-time data to improve process control and operational efficiency. The results demonstrated that the cation type and pH, with a P-value < 0.001, are the most significant factors affecting the RP. To achieve maximum RP, the pH should be set to 5, and the adsorbent amount should be in a range of 8.67–10 g L⁻¹, regardless of the initial concentration and type of ions (Pb²⁺, Mn²⁺, and Co²⁺). Then, evaluating MLAs showed that TRF, with a correlation coefficient exceeding 0.96, performs best for predicting RP, potentially reaching 0.99 at a split percentage around 80%. TRF uses real-time experimental data in water treatment systems to anticipate RP up to 98.75% and to activate alarms for RP below 80% using the KF principle.

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that 844 million people lack access to a basic supply of drinking water, and that 230 million people spend more than 30 minutes per day collecting water from improved sources, including piped water, boreholes, protected wells and springs, rainwater, and packaged or delivered water (WHO, Edition, 2011; Joseph et al., 2019; UNICEF, 2017). In developing countries such as Angola, Algeria, and Cameroon, increasing pollution is especially concerning because people lack the resources to treat polluted water or access clean drinking water (López and Toman, 2006). The problem of water quality is not limited to developing countries; even some developed countries, such as Italy, face significant issues due to heavy metals in their water resources (Triassi et al., 2023).

Importantly, the impact of water contamination extends beyond the immediate environment, affecting food sources and other parts of the community farther from the water source. Vegetables and fruits from a suburban industrial area in Bangladesh were found to contain elevated levels of heavy metals, including As, Cd, Pb, Mn, and Fe. Health risks were significant, particularly in relation to cancer, indicating unsuitability for growing certain vegetables (Sultana et al., 2017). As such, the discharge of heavy metals has a negative effect on the food chain. It is considerably more effective to control contamination in water resources than to deal with it later (Arunakumara and Zhang, 2008).

Adsorption (Arora, 2019), coagulation (Charentanyarak, 1999), electrocoagulation (Bazrafshan et al., 2015), membrane technologies (Qdais and Moussa, 2004) and catalytic treatments (Das and Poater, 2021) are among the various techniques for decontaminating heavy

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metals; each has pros and cons of its own. The adsorption method is ideal due to its low energy use, low cost, and ease of operation (Abas et al., 2013). While adsorption is inexpensive, it is not automated; chemical treatment is also inexpensive but polluting; electric-based treatment is more environmentally friendly but requires more energy and costs; membranes are clean but expensive; and photocatalysis offers notable environmental benefits; however, it is not highly cost-effective. Combining treatment techniques can enhance overall process efficiency and removal performance (Qasem et al., 2021). Therefore, they have been extensively targeted as viable methods for heavy metal decontamination in numerous studies. However, critical factors such as the type of adsorbent, adsorption mechanisms, and the incorporation of intelligent operational strategies remain important considerations and represent existing research gaps. Moreover, when waste materials are selected as adsorbents within an Integrated Waste Management System (IWMS) framework, the complexity of the operational process increases, requiring more advanced optimization and control approaches. The application of waste materials such as Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) as an adsorbent could be an example of circular economy principles in water treatment processes (Gheibi et al., 2025).

CDW consists of materials produced during construction, renovation, and demolition activities, including concrete, brick, sand, and gravel. The widespread use of concrete is drawing attention to inexpensive calcium-based adsorbents made from concrete waste. In the face of economic and environmental concerns, sustainable CDW reuse is crucial due to growing demand (Pallewatta et al., 2023). In Gheibi et al., CDW-derived adsorbents show complex heavy metal adsorption behavior because their surfaces are highly heterogeneous and porous, containing varied oxides such as CaO, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃. These irregular surface energies and diverse functional sites lead to multilayer and non-uniform adsorption, making the interaction between heavy metals and CDWs inherently complex (Gheibi et al., 2025). Due to this complex CDW behavior, statistical methods such as Response Surface Methodology (RSM) help assess key factors and predict adsorption process effectiveness (Anfar et al., 2020). RSM aims to build regression models for predicting responses, though accuracy may vary. However, these statistical methods are inherently static by design, and for dynamic analysis and real-time operation of adsorption systems, more advanced intelligent models based on artificial intelligence can be highly beneficial. Machine Learning Algorithms (MLAs) enhance prediction, offering smarter, more precise adsorption process control and enabling expert systems for efficient water purification (Han et al., 2025; Yaseen, 2021).

Pardakhti et al. (2017) employed MLAs to lessen the computational burden of molecular simulations for adsorbent screening. They used a range of machine learning algorithms, such as decision trees and support vector machines, to estimate methane uptake in Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs). In their study, 92 % of the dataset (130,398 MOFs) is used for training the model, while 8 % is used for testing. Yang et al. (2021) used 4420 data points from 1105 soils to create MLAs for heavy metal adsorption on soil. They discovered that the gradient boosting algorithm is the best decision tree algorithm for forecasting the adsorption of six heavy metals. To predict adsorption abilities and pollutant levels in water, independent and combined models are made. The Shapley additive explanation method helps identify important features. In their study, Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) are applied to interpret machine-learning models by quantifying how each input feature contributes to a prediction, enabling transparent assessment of variable importance, model behavior, and decision-making in complex environmental systems. Fanourgakis et al. (2019) proposed new descriptors for MLAs to predict the gas uptake capacities of nanoporous materials. Using void fractions of particles with defined van der Waals radii as descriptors, they assessed the random forest algorithm on a dataset of 4700 experimental MOFs. On the other hand, the results demonstrated that the proposed approach is generalizable beyond MOFs to other nanoporous materials. Zhu et al. (2021) apply MLAs to predict the adsorption of antibiotics on Carbon-based Materials (CBMs).

Comparing random forest, gradient boosting trees, and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), they found the random forest models most accurate. Relative importance analysis and partial dependence plots highlight key factors affecting adsorption, proving that MLAs are better at generalizing than traditional isotherm models. Pollutant adsorption on montmorillonite was assessed by Zhao et al. (2024a) using MLAs and Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations. They concentrated on the gradient-boosting decision tree model and examined the factors influencing adsorption because it matched the experimental results. DFT advances our understanding of montmorillonite-based adsorbents by examining interactions at different pH levels through MLAs and theoretical calculations.

According to the literature review (Fanourgakis et al., 2019; Pardakhti et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2022), it can be concluded that the application of MLAs is popular for evaluating heavy metal adsorption processes using CDW. However, the integration of the RSM with MLAs and the subsequent design of control systems has not been well explored in previous studies, which will be addressed in the present research. Due to the complexity of adsorption processes, RSM can help assess key factors and predict adsorption performance, but it is not suitable for real-time operational management because of its reliance on predefined experimental designs and limited adaptability to continuous conditions (Anfar et al., 2020). Several studies have utilized RSM and hybrid modeling approaches in adsorption processes. Using Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) and RSM, Okoye et al. (2025) modeled the adsorption of Erythrosine B (EB) dye and achieved a satisfactory level of efficiency. Despite their excellent prediction capabilities, they failed to develop an alarm or decision-making system, which is the focus of this work. Also, Brendler et al. (2003) used Microsoft Access to create a relational sorption database (RES3T) based on Surface Complexation Models (SCMs), which allowed for the modeling and extraction of data relevant to individual minerals. However, this study addressed the lack of a predictive system. Moreover, Zafar et al. (2022) employed full-factorial central composite design-based batch trials to estimate chromium adsorption onto modified maghemite nanoparticles using ANN and ANFIS. They did not, however, create an early warning or control system, which is a topic covered in this study.

The present study aims to:

- Conduct experimental tests for the adsorption of Pb²⁺, Mn²⁺, and Co²⁺ ions onto Low Density Concrete (LDC) by pH, metal type, Initial Concentration (IC), adsorbent mass, and contact time.
- Assess initial data using descriptive statistical methods for data categorization.
- Apply the RSM for sensitivity analysis and process optimization.
- Utilize MLAs to enhance the adsorption process and design a soft-sensor for forecasting removal performance using various algorithms.
- Develop a decision-making model to control the process using Knowledge Flow (KF) platform in WEKA and MATLAB software.

By creating an expert system for the adsorption of heavy metals onto low-density concrete waste and combining real-time data analysis and control, this work introduces a significant innovation. In contrast to earlier research, the system is built with WEKA's KF platform, which facilitates predictive process management and dynamic decision-making. This invention supports intelligent water treatment in line with Industry 4.0 principles by bridging the gap between smart automation and experimental adsorption.

2. Methodology

The complete research plan is shown in Fig. 1, and each stage is briefly explained to clarify the study's procedure. Step 1 entails conducting laboratory adsorption tests to comprehensively assess the

Fig. 1. The research roadmap of the present study.

removal behavior of Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} ions onto LDC. The Removal Percentages (RPs) that arise from adjusting each of the five operational variables: pH, metal type, IC, adsorbent mass, and contact time, are monitored as the system output during this phase. In order to find preliminary trends and possible parameter interactions, the gathered experimental data are categorized and represented in Step 2's descriptive statistical analysis. Step 3 employs RSM to conduct mathematical modeling, optimization, and sensitivity analysis utilizing historical data. Although it is not highly flexible for real-time process control, this phase quantifies the impact of each operational parameter on RP and provides preliminary prediction information. To develop more precise soft-sensor models that can capture nonlinear correlations between the five input parameters and RP, Step 4 expands the analysis by applying 20 MLAs (ESI Table 1). To find the most trustworthy predictors, these MLAs are thoroughly assessed using statistical and categorization markers.

Finally, Step 5 utilizes WEKA's Knowledge Flow (KF) platform to integrate the optimized machine learning models into an expert-based Decision Support System (DSS). In order to forecast RP, categorize performance levels, and produce alarm-based operational guidance for intelligent water treatment management, real-time data streams are handled in this final stage.

The selection of pH, metal type, initial concentration, adsorbent mass, and contact time as input variables for modeling heavy metal adsorption is well-grounded in adsorption theory. pH is a dominant factor because it controls both the adsorbent surface charge and the chemical speciation of metal ions through protonation-deprotonation mechanisms, thus determining electrostatic interactions and possible

metal precipitation. Initial concentration provides the mass-transfer driving force and influences adsorption kinetics and equilibrium capacity. Adsorbent mass dictates the number of available active sites, although its effect may become non-linear due to aggregation or site saturation. Contact time reflects the kinetic progression of adsorption and indicates whether the process is diffusion- or reaction-controlled. Metal type is also crucial because ionic characteristics such as radius, hydration energy, and coordination behavior govern the affinity of metals for the adsorbent. Together, these variables capture the essential thermodynamic and kinetic properties of adsorption systems, making them necessary for accurate modeling and optimization (Raji et al., 2023). Therefore, these parameters were selected as inputs for the models in the present study.

2.1. Adsorption process

A produced CDW-derived adsorbent was used in the investigation by Gheibi et al. (2025) to decontaminate under various settings. These conditions included variable pH, IC of the metal ions, adsorbent mass, and time. All experiments were carried out at room temperature using the protocols provided by Gheibi et al. (2025). Following each experiment, which was carried out in a reactor with a volume of 15 mL, Eq. (1) was used to determine the RP:

$$RP(\%) = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

C_0 : Initial concentration (mg L^{-1})

C_e : Experimental concentration after adsorption (mg L^{-1})

The study systematically investigates how these factors affect the CDW adsorbent's adsorption effectiveness. The examined pH ranges that are examined span from acidic to approximately neutral, which is important since pH significantly impacts the metal oxidation state and the adsorbent's surface charge. The optimal amount required for maximal ion removal was determined by varying the adsorbent's mass. To understand the adsorption process kinetics and determine the time required to reach equilibrium, contact time was varied. Additionally, the initial metal ion concentrations were adjusted in order to assess the

Table 1
Ranges of input variables used in the modeling practices of this study.

Parameter	Unit	Min	Max
Heavy metal type	—	$\text{Pb}^{2+} = 1$, $\text{Co}^{2+} = 2$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+} = 3$	
pH	—	2	5
Initial concentration	mg L^{-1}	10	200
Adsorbent mass	g	0.02	0.15
Contact time	min	0	120

adsorbent's capacity and effectiveness at various contaminant concentrations.

In this research, using a One-Factor-At-a-Time (OFAT) approach, the study systematically varied pH, adsorbent mass and contact time to investigate the adsorption behavior of heavy metals. The present investigation used OFAT to isolate each factor's effect before interaction modeling as per the outcomes of Gheibi et al. (2025). Its 66 data points were then employed to support RSM-based analysis and subsequent MLAs modeling. The ranges of input data applied in this study are shown in Table 1. Experiments were carried out at an acidic pH range of 2.0 to 5.0. In the first step, 15 mL of a 10 mg L⁻¹ metal ion solution was mixed with 0.1 g of a fixed dose of LDC adsorbent, kept at 25 °C, and agitated at 400 rpm. Adsorbent mass ranged from 0.02 to 0.15 g, while contact time ranged from 0 to 120 min. Following the specified contact time, samples were spun for 10 min at 3000 rpm. Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) was used to determine the residual concentrations of heavy metals using element-specific wavelengths for Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺. Each metal ion was then subjected to isothermal adsorption studies across a concentration range of 10-200 mg L⁻¹. For use in data mining and machine learning analysis, the whole dataset gathered from these tests was assembled. The schematic plan of the experiments conducted in this study is presented in ESI Fig. 1. ESI Fig. 1 illustrates the experimental workflow used in this study. Aqueous solutions containing Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ ions were first prepared at controlled pH. A known mass of LDC powder was then added and mixed for a selected contact time to allow adsorption. After reaction, solid-liquid separation was performed using centrifugation, and the clarified supernatant was collected. The remaining metal concentrations were subsequently quantified by AAS, while the separated solid phase contained the adsorbed heavy metal ions (Gheibi et al., 2025).

2.2. Data analysis

The initial experimental data are presented using split heat map plots. These visualizations illustrate the effects of paired parameters against RP. This categorization allows for a preliminary sensitivity analysis of the input parameters. However, a more comprehensive sensitivity analysis will be conducted in subsequent steps using more precise statistical techniques. All analyses in this section were performed using OriginPro 2021 software.

2.3. RSM technique

In the present study, historical data analysis as part of the RSM method in Design Expert 7.0.0 is applied. The mathematical model considers five input factors: pH, metal type, IC, adsorbent mass, and time, with RP as the output. In the RSM analysis, curve fitting is first performed to identify the best equation for predicting RP. Then, ANOVA analysis is conducted to determine the most significant factors. Finally, after a sensitivity analysis of the key features in the experiments, the optimization process is performed. The general form of the mathematical equation in the curve-fitting process is demonstrated in Eq. (2) (Mahmoudi Jalali et al., 2023).

$$Z = a_0 + a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + \dots + a_nX_n + a_{12}X_1X_2 + a_{13}X_1X_3 + \dots + a_{1n}X_1X_n + \dots + a_{(n-1)n}X_{n-1}X_n + a_{11}X_1^2 + \dots + a_{nn}X_n^2 \quad (2)$$

2.4. MLAs

In the next stage of the study, 20 algorithms in WEKA software version 3.9.6, including Function Gaussian Process (FGP), Function Linear Regression (FLR), Function Multilayer Perceptron (FMLP), Function Simple Linear Regression (FSLR), Function SMOreg (F SMOreg), lazy Instance-Based K (IBK), lazy KStar, lazy Locally Weighted

Learning (LWL), Meta Additive Regression (MAR), Meta Bagging (MB), Meta Random Committee (MRC), Meta Randomizable Filtered Classifier (MRFC), Meta Random Sub Space (MRSS), Meta Regression by Discretization (MRD), Rules Decision Table (RDT), Rules M5 Rules (RM5R), Trees Decision Stump (TDS), Trees M5P (TM5P), Trees Random Forest (TRF), and Trees Random Tree (TRT) (Hall and Reutemann., 2025). The descriptions of all the applied algorithms are presented in ESI Table 1. In the first step, all the algorithms are compared for the adsorption data analysis in 60 % Split Percentage (SP) of training and 40 % for testing. In machine learning, the SP describes splitting a dataset into discrete portions, usually for testing and training (Hall and Reutemann., 2025). The 60/40 split was initially selected to perform a stricter early-stage screening of the 20 machine-learning algorithms. Using a larger test portion (40 %) increases the evaluation pressure on each model, helping identify only the most robust algorithms under limited training data. After this screening, the selected models were further optimized, and an 80/20 split was later applied to maximize training data and achieve the highest predictive accuracy.

Then, the results are compared together according to statistical indicators, including Correlation Coefficient (CC), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Relative Absolute Error (RAE), and Root Relative Squared Error (RRSE) (Horn, 1993). All mathematical expressions of the indicators are presented in ESI Table 2. In this stage, the algorithms will be screened, and the ones with CC > 0.92 will be selected. In the next step, due to the evaluation of selected algorithms, some other classification indicators (ESI Table 3), including True Positive Rate (TP Rate), False Positive Rate (FP Rate), Precision, Recall, F-measure, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Area, and Precision-Recall Curve (PRC) Area (Poh et al., 2018). The algorithms classified samples into two classes (C₀ and C₁) derived from the continuous RP removal values using model-specific, data-driven decision rules in WEKA software. Standard classification metrics were then employed solely to benchmark the performance of different MLAs. Finally, the most accurate algorithms, as per statistical and classification indicators, will be tuned using hyperparameter optimization. Plus, it should be noted that the application of multiple machine learning algorithms (Liu et al., 2024) can serve as a promising approach for controlling complex processes under unpredictable conditions. For instance, in cases involving unknown waste materials, this multidimensional technique can enhance the system's adaptability and overall intelligence.

2.5. Expert system design

Further, the optimal performance of MLAs is implemented as an expert system with a knowledge flow package of WEKA software. In the analysis, a system is developed for online data mining of adsorption processes in water treatment facilities, including urban water treatment plants and mine drainage treatment systems. All data analysis and categorization plus mining of them are executed by KF toolboxes. Finally, visualization and reporting tools are arranged there (Hall and

Table 2

The results of ANOVA assessment in the present study.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-value
Model	33,730.54	5	6746.1	69.12	< 0.0001
A-Metal type	15,852.18	1	15,852.18	162.4	< 0.0001
B-pH	12,582.62	1	12,582.62	128.91	< 0.0001
C-M	5371.36	1	5371.36	55.03	< 0.0001
D-Time	332.39	1	332.39	3.4	0.07
E-IC	396.54	1	396.54	4.06	0.05

Table 3

The optimal suggestions for effective factors in the adsorption of heavy metals onto LDC.

Metal type	pH	M (g)	Time (min)	IC (mg L ⁻¹)	RP (%)
Pb ²⁺	5	0.13	33.5	35	99
Co ²⁺	5	0.15	110	10	99
Mn ²⁺	5	0.15	120	10	81

Reutemann., 2025).

After designing the KF, the model was further extended into a control dashboard using MATLAB 2019b. The initial assessments were conducted in WEKA; however, to enhance dynamism, flexibility, and implementation capability, the model was subsequently redesigned and developed in the MATLAB environment. The model architecture begins with a CSV Loader that imports experimental data, followed by an RP Class Assigner that categorizes RP values into four predefined classes including [11 %–33 %], [33 %–55 %], [55 %–77 %], and [77 %–99 %]. A Fold Maker then partitions the dataset into training (70 %) and testing (30 %) subsets. A baseline MLA is trained first, after which a Sensitivity Analyzer systematically evaluates key RF hyperparameters to identify the optimal configuration. The optimized MLA model performs continuous RP prediction, which is further translated into discrete RP classes for decision-making. These predictions feed into an Alarm Manager that detects low-RP conditions and triggers alerts. Finally, a comprehensive

Dashboard visualizes performance metrics, class distributions, and sensitivity outcomes, while a Results Exporter saves all generated reports and prediction tables.

3. Results and discussions

In this section, the experimental data were first analyzed using statistical methods to evaluate variations under different experimental conditions. The primary objective was to identify patterns and fluctuations in the data. In the next phase, RSM and sensitivity analysis were applied to determine the optimal operating conditions. However, the resulting model at this stage was not suitable for real-time prediction and dynamic control of the heavy metal adsorption process. Therefore, in the following step, machine learning models were implemented for both regression (prediction) and classification (screening of removal percentages) tasks. Finally, the developed model was integrated into a dynamic system using the KF concept to serve as an expert-based, real-time warning system for adsorption processes.

3.1. Experiments and data analysis

A set of heat maps showing the experimental association between RP and other effective factors for heavy metals treatment is shown in Fig. 2 (a-d). Before RSM and machine learning models were applied, heat maps were utilized as an initial sensitivity analysis to visually identify

Fig. 2. The heat map of data categorization of adsorption parameter for different metal types (Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺) vs. RP for (a) pH, 2 < pH < 5, (b) adsorbent amount, 0.02 g < adsorbent (g) < 0.15 g, (c) time, 10 min < Time (min) < 120 min, (d) initial concentration, 10 mg L⁻¹ < concentration (mg L⁻¹) < 200 mg L⁻¹. General conditions are pH = 5, IC = 10 mg L⁻¹ of each heavy metals, mass of adsorbent = 0.1 g of LDC powder, contact time = 30 min, and solution volume = 15 mL.

parameter interactions and early trends in adsorption behavior. This phase made it possible to identify the variables that have the most significant effect, especially the significant impact of pH on removal performance. It also made it easier to identify nonlinear or metal-specific trends that are not visible from raw data alone. Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} specific trends have been clearly presented in the Results section, which has been updated to highlight the experimentally derived results.

Fig. 2(a) shows how pH affects the RP of various heavy metals with values ranging from 2 to 5. Based on heavy metals solubility product constant (K_{sp}), the pH range of 2-5 was analyzed. Because Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} at a concentration of 200 mg L⁻¹ precipitate at pH of ~ 7.5, 7.79, and 8.82, respectively, this concentration was taken as the highest used in experiments. As pH increases above 5, ions form metal hydroxide precipitates ($M(OH)_2$), reducing adsorption effectiveness (Harris, 2010). To prevent precipitation, a maximum pH of 5 was selected. The adsorption of all heavy metals increased as pH increased. Although pH is the main driver, sensitivity analysis provides a more nuanced assessment of other factors, like IC and adsorbent mass, to better understand their respective contributions. To ascertain if a solid will precipitate from a solution, precipitation control calculations use the K_{sp} . The K_{sp} formulation is $K_{sp} = [A^{n+}]^m[B^{m-}]^n$ for a salt A_mB_n , which dissociates as $A_mB_n \rightleftharpoons mA^{n+} + nB^{m-}$. The present study compares the ion product (Q) to K_{sp} by computing it using the real ion concentrations in solution. A precipitate occurs and the solution is supersaturated if $Q > K_{sp}$. There is no precipitation if $Q \leq K_{sp}$. With the help of this technique, precipitation in chemical reactions can be precisely predicted and controlled, guaranteeing stability or causing solid formation as necessary (Akitsu, 2017; Clifford, 2002).

Fig. 2(b) shows dependency of adsorbed amounts to amount of sorbent used (solid/liquid ration). Adsorbed amount is increasing with amount of adsorbent, which is logical. Fig. 2(c) presents the impact of metal ion concentration on RP at different times, showing a dynamic interplay between concentration and time. These findings align with previous studies that emphasize the role of pH in optimizing adsorption efficiency, as discussed below. The same results on the effects of time-pH are evaluated in the adsorption process by Chen et al. (2011). They demonstrated that the adsorption of Cd^{2+} on a type of bentonite achieves equilibrium in 50 min, with increasing pH enhancing adsorption capacity and specific pH levels and contact times significantly influencing the adsorption process (Chen et al., 2011). Likewise, Jamaloi et al. (2025) demonstrated that increasing the pH during the adsorption of Co^{2+} ions using bone powder modified with polypyrrole and polyethylene glycol enhances the removal efficiency. Plus, Pooladi et al. (2024) reported that increasing the pH from 2 to 6 improved the adsorption performance of Pb^{2+} onto a biosorbent derived from Cardita bicolor shell. Similarly, Zadeh & Jafari (2024) demonstrated that increasing the pH from 2 to 6 significantly improves the adsorption efficiency of Pb^{2+} onto an activated carbon/alginate/ Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanocomposite.

According to Fig. 2(d), with increasing IC, the percentage of IC adsorbed is increasing in Pb^{2+} and reversely in Co^{2+} . While, in Mn^{2+} , the fluctuations was high and it shows low correlation between IC and RP in the case of Mn^{2+} and therefore, the effects of other features should be evaluated in multidimensional assessment. Notable variations in RP imply that pH is an important factor in metal adsorption. This uncertainty in Mn^{2+} adsorption patterns with IC emphasizes the need for multidimensional analysis that takes into account several factors at once, including pH and contact time. However, as Fig. 2(b-d) demonstrates, the RP is also influenced by other variables, such as time, IC, and adsorbent mass. Since variations in the heat map are more noticeable when pH is altered than when other parameters are considered, this implies that pH might be one of the most influential factor in the adsorption of heavy metals from water supplies by LDC. This result is in line with earlier research conducted by Kavand et al. (2014) and Xu et al. (2013). However, this research needs more validation utilizing exact methodologies, especially taking into account the pH changes during the

adsorption process (not just using the initial pH value prior to adsorption).

As observed in the present study, LDC exhibits higher efficiency in the decontamination of Pb^{2+} compared to Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . Similarly, Nemati et al. (2021) reported that Pb^{2+} demonstrated superior adsorption performance over Ag^{3+} when using activated carbon derived from Citrus limon tree leaves. Furthermore, Aboli et al. (2020) showed that Pb^{2+} outperformed Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions in adsorption onto activated carbon prepared from Citrus limetta leaves. Lastly, Koohzad et al. (2019) confirmed that Pb^{2+} had a higher adsorption efficiency than As^{3+} when using activated carbon produced from Tamarix leaves. These similar findings across multiple studies further support the validity of the current results.

3.2. Optimization and sensitive analysis

Curve fitting using RSM was used to further validate the experimental patterns seen in Fig. 2, and the outcomes are compiled in ESI Table 4. The linear model recommended by the RSM technique has an R^2 value of 0.85 and a predicted R^2 of 0.80, as shown in ESI Table 4. According to these findings, 85 % of the variability in the response variable can be explained by the linear model, and the anticipated R^2 value of 0.80 indicates a respectable degree of predictive power. Regression coefficients of 0.80 are deemed insufficiently dependable for precise prediction in industrial applications. This suggests that more reliable prediction models are required. Because machine learning algorithms can handle complicated, non-linear interactions in data, they may, therefore, be a good alternative for improving adsorption performance prediction. The obtained equation for the RSM technique is demonstrated in Eq. (3). According to the formula, it can be understood that with different values of metal type (Pb^{2+} : 1, Co^{2+} : 2, and Mn^{2+} : 3), the RP could be calculated in different pH, IC, adsorbent mass (M), and time. The coefficients of different factors are different because of their different scales and units. Similarly, Urréjola-Madrinán et al. (2022) proposed a linear model to describe the adsorption of Cr(VI) using spirulina algae biomass. In their study, they characterized the adsorption capacity using a linear relationship involving the IC and the mass of the adsorbent.

$$RP(\%) = -19.69 + (-18.98 \times Metaltype) + (18.83 \times pH) + (360.49 \times M) + (0.08 \times Time) + (-0.05 \times IC) \quad (3)$$

According to ESI Fig. 2(a), it is clear that the experimental RP is distributed around the normal diagram, and therefore, the model follows the normal statistical distribution. Also, in the study of Ahmadzadeh & Hemmati (2025), the response of Pb^{2+} adsorption onto zinc-based MOFs-derived carbon indicates that the residuals are normally distributed. As shown in ESI Fig. 2(b), standardized residuals with values between -3 and 3 indicate that most data points are in a line with traditional regression analysis predictions, implying a generally normal distribution and adequate model. Anything outside of this range might need further examination for abnormalities in the data and model validity. Likewise, analysis of ESI Fig. 2(c) reveals a close alignment between actual and predicted values, showing good fit and random distribution around the regression line. At the same time, there are some differences between the actual and prediction amounts. This difference indicates potential for further model refinement to enhance predictive accuracy.

Lambda values in ESI Fig. 2(d) from the Box-Cox diagram help determine the best data transformation for model accuracy. The lambda values are: Current = 1, Best = 0.73, High = 1.22, and Low = 0.3. This means that the current transformation (lambda = 1) works well enough, but adjusting it to 0.73 could improve model accuracy. The range (0.3 to 1.22) shows how sensitive the model is to the lambda value, which can affect data normalization quality. Since the current lambda provides good results, no further transformation is needed (Sreeharsha et al.,

Table 4
Summary of various studies on the application of MLAs in adsorption processes.

Adsorbent	Adsorbate	Machine learning model	Statistical indicators	Reference
Metal-organic frameworks	As ^{3+/5+} , Cd ²⁺ , Cr ⁶⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺	Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT)	R ² =0.921-0.962 for 6 heavy metals	(Wang et al., 2025)
Biochar	Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , As ³⁺	Random forest	R ² = 0.973	(Zhu et al., 2019)
Bentonite	Pb ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , and chromium ions	eXtreme Gradient Boosting Regression (XGB)	Train R ² = 0.995 Test R ² = 0.9359	(Guo et al., 2024)
Hydrochar	Pb ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Sb ³⁺ , Sb ⁵⁺ , CrO ₄ ²⁻ , UO ₂ ²⁺	Gradient boosting decision tree	R ² = 0.93-0.98	(Zhao et al., 2023)
Clay minerals	Cd ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ and Co ²⁺	Extreme Gradient Boosting	R ² = 0.977	(Zhao et al., 2024b)
LDC	Pb ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺	Trees Random Forest	R ² = 0.98	This study

2020). Therefore, the existing condition is used for modeling.

As we discussed about our normal distribution of results, also, Danmaliki et al. (2017) showed that the adsorption process in the desulfurization on nickel/activated carbon follows a normal distribution. A similar conclusion had Saini et al. (2019), who studied Cd²⁺ adsorption onto C₁₆₋₆₋₁₆ incorporated mesoporous MCM-41. This will be further elaborated in the following sections.

The results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) are presented in Table 2. According to the table, the p-value of the model is <0.0001, indicating that the model is highly significant. Among all the influential factors, pH, metal ion type and mass of adsorbent exhibit significant effects on RP with p-values < 0.0001. Specifically, the most substantial

influences are attributed to metal ion type (162.4) and pH (128.91). In contrast, the impacts of IC and reaction time on RP are relatively minimal. The reason for these is that relative narrow intervals of values for IC and reaction time was studied in the experimental setup.

Sensitivity analysis was performed to visualize the interactions and comparative influence of pH and metal ion type, which were identified as dominant components in the ANOVA results. The sensitivity analysis results are displayed in Fig. 3. The adsorption process efficiency of Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ varies significantly. These variations can be related to variances in their ionic radii. In particular, it is clear that Pb²⁺ has higher adsorption effectiveness than both Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺, indicating that ionic radius has an effect on the adsorption mechanism. Also, Dong

Fig. 3. The sensitive analysis of pH vs. mass of adsorbent as per (a) Pb²⁺ RP, (b) Co²⁺ RP, and (c) Mn²⁺ RP.

et al. (2007) conducted research demonstrating that the adsorption capacity of Pb^{2+} exceeds that of Co^{2+} on various metal oxides and organic materials found in natural surface coatings. Their findings corroborate the results observed in the present study. This underscores the consistent pattern of Pb^{2+} exhibiting higher adsorption capacity compared to Co^{2+} across different materials studied in both investigations.

The differences in maximum RP values seen among various metal ions are directly caused by these ideal parameter combinations. The optimal conditions for adsorbing Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} ions onto LDC are summarized in Table 3. According to the table, the ideal pH and mass of the adsorbent are consistently 5 and 0.13-0.15 (ESI Fig. 3a-c), respectively, for all ions. Specifically, LDC demonstrates remarkable efficacy for Pb^{2+} ions, three times higher IC and reaching maximum adsorption capacity in three times less contact time compared to Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions.

In the following, based on the model, the maximum adsorption efficiency for Co^{2+} ions can reach up to 99 %, whereas for Mn^{2+} ions, it reaches 81 % (ESI Fig. 3b and c). These results underscore the varying adsorption capacities of LDC for different metal ions, reflecting its potential as an effective adsorbent in environmental remediation processes. Similar to the results of our study, Çelebi et al., 2020

demonstrated that the optimal removal efficiency for Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions occurs at a pH of approximately 5 during their experiments. Moreover, Meena et al. (2024) demonstrated that As^{3+} adsorption onto cross-linked chitosan-tripolyphosphate nanoparticles achieves optimal capacity at approximately pH 5. Plus, as per the study of Nyirenda et al. (2022), the maximum adsorption of Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions onto the silver-silica nanocomposite supported by activated carbon occurred at approximately pH 5.5, aligning with the findings of the current study.

The RSM model's structure is intrinsically static and cannot self-train, update, or adapt when new data or operational disruptions arise, despite the fact that it attained respectable statistical accuracy. RSM is primarily appropriate for mechanistic interpretation and sensitivity analysis rather than real-time automation because it depends on predetermined experimental designs and established polynomial equations. The current study, on the other hand, calls for a dynamic predictive engine that can support automated control actions and continually learn from incoming sensor data. By recording nonlinear behaviors, retraining with fresh data, and integrating straight into the KF platform, where real-time prediction, categorization, and alarm management are implemented MLAs overcome the limitations of RSM. Therefore, MLAs are chosen not only to increase accuracy but also to enable an intelligent system that is

Fig. 4. The outputs of machine learning analysis based on (a) CC of 20 algorithms and categorizations, (b) RAE % and RRSE % for 20 algorithms, (c) MAE and RMSE indicators for 20 algorithms, and (d) classification performance metrics in three selected algorithms. Abbreviations - CC: Correlation Coefficient, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, RMSE: Root Mean Squared Error, RAE: Relative Absolute Error, and RRSE: Root Relative Squared Error, FGP: Function Gaussian Process, FLR: Function Linear Regression, FMLP: Function Multilayer Perceptron, FSLR: Function Simple Linear Regression, F SMOreg: Function SMOreg, IBK: Lazy Instance-Based K, KStar: Lazy KStar, LWL: Lazy Locally Weighted Learning, MAR: Meta Additive Regression, MB: Meta Bagging, MRC: Meta Random Committee, MRFC: Meta Randomizable Filtered Classifier, MRSS: Meta Random Sub Space, MRD: Meta Regression by Discretization, RDT: Rules Decision Table, RM5R: Rules M5 Rules, TDS: Trees Decision Stump, TM5P: Trees M5P, TRF: Trees Random Forest, TRT: Trees Random Tree.

compatible with Industry 4.0, something that RSM is essentially unable to achieve.

3.3. Machine learning algorithms

Previously, we modeled the RP values based on several effective factors, including pH, metal type, IC, adsorbent mass, and time in the solution. We also conducted a sensitivity analysis to determine the most significant factors affecting RP among these parameters. Initially, we developed a regression-based model, which, however, required frequent adjustments. MLAs can overcome this limitation by enabling automated training processes based on input data at specific intervals. A promising substitute for more accurate prediction is provided by machine learning algorithms, as the linear regression model is unable to adequately capture intricate nonlinear interactions.

In the following sections, various MLAs was explored to predict RP based on these effective features as dynamic soft-sensors. Both statistical and classification indicators were examined for the different algorithms, and the selected MLAs was tuned accordingly. The results of the MLA analysis are shown in Fig. 4 and ESI Table 5. According to Fig. 4(a), it is evident that three algorithms, FMLP, lazy IBK, and TRF, exhibit a CC exceeding 0.92. These algorithms are considered the best performers at this stage, having been trained with 60 % of the data. A correlation coefficient above 0.92 indicates a strong relationship between the predicted (by the mentioned algorithms) and actual values (experimental results) in a machine learning model. Physically, this means the model's predictions closely match the water treatment processes through adsorption technique, suggesting high predictive accuracy. It implies that changes in the input variables are strongly linked to the changes in the target variable, allowing the model to make reliable predictions (Eftekhari et al., 2021).

According to Fig. 4(b), when examining the RAE %, which measures the total absolute error in relation to a simple predictor, lazy IBK achieves the lowest RAE % at 27.73, followed by TRF at 30.11. Figs. 4 (a-c) indicate that these models have a lower proportion of error relative to a naive benchmark model. TDS, with a RAE % of 91.91, shows the highest relative error, further indicating its inefficiency compared to simpler models. In Fig. 4(b), the RRSE %, which normalizes the RMSE by the standard deviation of the actual values, is lowest for lazy IBK (38.91) and TRF (39.54), suggesting these models have a smaller proportion of squared error relative to other models. TDS, with an RRSE % of 93.22, again has the highest value, emphasizing its poor performance. Regarding the MAE indicator in Fig. 4(c), which indicates the average magnitude of the errors in a set of predictions, lazy IBK stands out with the lowest MAE of 6.48, followed by TRF at 7.03. These low values imply that, on average, the predictions made by these models are very close to the actual values. Conversely, TDS has the highest MAE at 21.47, indicating larger average prediction errors and lower accuracy. The RMSE, which provides an indication (Fig. 4c) of the model's error magnitude and is more sensitive to outliers, is also lowest for lazy IBK (9.86) and TRF (10.02). These low RMSE values highlight the models' robust performance in minimizing error. TDS, with the highest RMSE of 23.64, again demonstrates the poorest performance among the algorithms in this aspect.

Finally, TRF and lazy IBK emerge as the top performers across various metrics. TRF achieves the highest correlation coefficient and low error rates, establishing it as a reliable and accurate model. Lazy IBK demonstrates excellent performance with the lowest MAE and RMSE, highlighting its high predictive accuracy and robustness. Additionally, FMLP exhibits commendable efficiency following lazy IBK and TRF, achieving approximately 0.92 CC.

In a study by Yaqub et al. (2020), it was demonstrated that an ANN with an R^2 value of 0.97 is the most effective technique for predicting the removal efficiency of Cr^{6+} purification using polymer inclusion membranes. The origin of ANN is similar to that of the FMLP. In the present research, FMLP has also been identified as one of the best algorithms for

estimating adsorption efficiency. Interestingly, in a study by Hafsa et al. (2021), the CC was calculated to be approximately 0.97 using the TRF algorithm for predicting arsenic removal from water resources. This result is comparable to the findings of the present research regarding the TRF algorithm.

Moreover, Jaskulak et al. (2020) compared the performance of ANN with RSM for predicting Cd^{2+} removal efficiency by *Sinapis alba L.* Similar to the present study, their analysis demonstrated that ANN, specifically with the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, achieved a CC of approximately 0.99, which was higher than that of RSM.

In the present study, it has been proven that TRF, lazy IBK, and FMLP algorithms exhibit higher accuracy in estimating RP compared to RSM. However, it is noteworthy that the ANN algorithm involves extensive computational stages. At an industrial level, utilizing algorithms such as TRF or lazy IBK can significantly reduce prediction time and investment costs in smart infrastructure development.

Fig. 4(d) shows that FMLP outperforms lazy IBK and TRF in key areas. FMLP has a higher TP Rate (0.825) than lazy IBK and TRF (0.80), indicating better accuracy in detecting real positives. Additionally, FMLP has a lower FP Rate (0.21) compared to lazy IBK and TRF (0.28), resulting in fewer false positives and increased reliability.

FMLP performs slightly better than lazy IBK and TRF in precision (FMLP: 0.80) and recall (FMLP: 0.82). This means FMLP is more accurate and reliable in predicting positives, making it preferable in applications where precision and recall are crucial. Also, the same results are obtained from F-measure and MCC indicators analysis.

In terms of ROC Area, which measures the ability of the classifier to distinguish between classes, lazy IBK and TRF show similar performance with scores of 0.84 and 0.84, respectively, slightly higher than FMLP's 0.81. However, PRC Area, which focuses on precision and recall across thresholds, highlights TRF's superiority with the highest score of 0.83, followed by lazy IBK at 0.82 and FMLP at 0.78. Therefore, in metrics directly related to classification accuracy, such as TP Rate, FP Rate, Precision, Recall, F-measure, and MCC, FMLP generally performs better than lazy IBK and TRF. Lazy IBK and TRF, on the other hand, perform marginally better in the ROC and PRC regions; TRF has the highest PRC area, indicating superior precision-recall performance across various thresholds. The exact application requirements ultimately determine which approach is best, especially whether improved ROC and PRC performance or increased precision and recall are more important. Based on engineering judgment and operational requirements, these three algorithms should operate simultaneously on the dashboard, allowing operators to decide their use based on experience.

Al-Sakkari et al. (2023) conducted an impressive study in which they used decision tree classification models and machine learning models to estimate the efficiency of adsorption-based carbon dioxide capture materials. Their findings attained recall, precision, and F-measure values of 1. The performance of the models in this study varied due to differences in data sources and experimental setups. Yang et al. (2022) applied a decision tree classification model for acetylene adsorption by MOFs. They found that the model achieved recall, precision, and F-measure values of 86.40, 92.0, and 88.80, respectively. The recall and F-measure values reported by Yang et al. (2022) are similar to the results of the present study.

The impact of varying the SP on the operation of the selected algorithms (FMLP, lazy IBK, and TRF) can be analyzed through statistical metrics to understand their robustness and trustworthiness under different conditions (Fig. 5).

According to Fig. 5(a), TRF steadily achieves the highest CC, reaching up to 0.99 at SP=80 %, demonstrating a very strong linear relationship regardless of the SP. FMLP and lazy IBK also illustrate large CC amounts, with FMLP peaking around 0.95 at SP=65 % and SP=80 %, and lazy IBK reaching 0.96 at SP=75 %. However, TRF generally outperforms the other two algorithms in terms of CC, suggesting superior reliability in its predictions.

In consideration of Fig. 5(b), MAE indicates the average magnitude

Fig. 5. The results of machine learning analysis in different SP % = 60 % - 80 % based on (a) CC, (b) MAE, (c) RMSE, (d) RAE % and (e) RRSE %.

of errors in the predictions. At SP=60 %, lazy IBK has the lowest MAE (6.48), followed by TRF (7.03) and FMLP (8.06). As SP increases to 80 %, TRF shows significant improvement, achieving the lowest MAE (4.75), indicating enhanced accuracy with a larger training set. Lazy IBK also shows improvement, with an MAE of 4.88 at SP=80 %, while FMLP's MAE decreases to 7.28. TRF and lazy IBK benefit more from larger training sets than FMLP, with TRF showing superior performance. Lazy IBK also improves significantly with more data, while FMLP generally achieves acceptable results, especially at higher split percentages. This highlights the importance of tuning and larger training sets for algorithm performance.

According to Fig. 5(c) and d, at SP 60 %, lazy IBK has the lowest RMSE (9.86), TRF follows (10.02). At SP 80 %, both improve (lazy IBK: 7.46, TRF: 6.68). RAE at SP 60 %, lazy IBK leads (27.73 %); at SP 80 %, TRF improves (19.87 %), surpassing lazy IBK (20.43 %). RRSE at SP 60 %, lazy IBK is lowest (38.91 %); at SP 80 %, TRF is best (26.35 %). TRF and lazy IBK benefit more from larger training sets than FMLP. As mentioned before, finally, the present study applied TRF for creating the expert system because of its superior performance in precision-recall metrics, particularly in achieving the highest PRC area, which indicates its effectiveness across varying decision thresholds. TRF's consistent reliability in these aspects made it the preferred choice for developing the expert system, aligning with the operational requirements and practical application needs of the system.

Table 4 shows that MLAs such as Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT) (Wang et al., 2025), Random Forest (Zhu et al., 2019), and XGBoost (Guo et al., 2024) achieve high accuracy ($R^2 \approx 0.92-0.99$) across diverse adsorbents, indicating their strong ability to capture complex adsorption behavior. However, the results also suggest that the surface chemistry and heterogeneity of each adsorbent strongly influence which algorithm performs best. Materials like biochar, bentonite, and hydrochar-rich (Zhao et al., 2023) in functional groups and porous structures-align well with tree-based models capable of handling nonlinear adsorption patterns. The present study similarly shows that LDC, with its heterogeneous CaO-SiO₂-Al₂O₃ surface, is best modeled by TRF ($R^2 = 0.98$). This highlights a key future direction: identifying which surface-adsorbate interaction patterns correspond to specific MLA architectures, enabling more targeted and mechanistic model selection in adsorption research.

3.4. Knowledge flow system design

The next obvious step was to integrate the top-performing model into a real-time expert decision support system after identifying TRF as the top performer. In the following, with the application of KF tool, an expert system is designed to predict the adsorption performance and process control as an alarm management system. Fig. 6(a) illustrates a comprehensive workflow for constructing and evaluating a machine learning model using a visual programming tool with WEKA. The process begins with the CSVLoader, which imports the dataset from a CSV file. This dataset is then passed to the ClassAssigner node, which designates the class attribute necessary for supervised learning tasks, setting the stage for the model training. Afterward, the Cross-ValidationFoldMaker node divides the dataset into training and testing sets through cross-validation. This method ensures that the model is validated on different subsets of the data, promoting a reliable estimation of its performance. The core of the modeling process is handled by the RandomForest node, which applies the TRF. This ensemble learning technique constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their outputs to produce more accurate and stable predictions. To facilitate further evaluation and analysis, the PredictionAppender node attaches the predictions generated by the TRF model to the dataset. Following this, the RemoveWithValue node filters out instances with lower than 80 % removal efficiency of different heavy metal ions in the system. The model's performance is then rigorously evaluated by the ClassifierPerformanceEvaluator, which uses metrics like accuracy, precision, and recall to assess the classifier's effectiveness. All the analyses of the expert system are set on TRF with 80 % SP, which was optimized before. For visualization purposes, the ModelPerformanceChart node creates charts, such as ROC curves, to illustrate the model's performance graphically. Meanwhile, the ScatterPlotMatrix node generates a scatter plot matrix, enabling the visualization of relationships between different attributes within the dataset (Hall and Reutemann., 2025).

Fig. 6(b) is a scatter plot displaying the relationship between pH and mass (g) of adsorbent. The data points are color-coded according to their class values, as indicated by the gradient color bar at the bottom (RP), ranging from 33.76 % to 98.75 %. The points vary in size, suggesting different weights or frequencies. A significant concentration of data points is observed at higher pH values (around 4.5 to 5), with a wide range of masses. This shows that the data are clearly classified, with pH values of 4-5 corresponding to higher adsorbent masses, typically in the

Fig. 6. The outputs of the designed expert system based on (a) schematic plan of the expert system, (b) classifications by TRF in pH vs. Mass of adsorbent, (c) classifications by TRF in pH vs. contact time, (d) control system analysis by time-heavy metal type.

0.10-0.15 g range, aligning with the finding that pH and mass are dominant factors controlling removal performance in LDC-based adsorption. Fig. 6(c) is another scatter plot showing the relationship between pH and time (min). Similar to Fig. 6(b), the data points are color-coded based on class values with the same color gradient. The distribution of points suggests that higher pH levels (around 4 to 5) correspond to a broader range of time values, from around 10 to 120 min. There are fewer data points at lower pH levels (around 2 to 3.5), indicating that these conditions are less common or less significant in the dataset. The largest RP values happen in the pH 4–5 range because

adsorption is chemically strongest there, where metal ions bond more successfully and the LDC surface is less protonated. In order to capture significant adsorption behavior, the majority of isothermal studies were carried out at pH 4-5. WEKA displays fewer data points in the pH 2–3.5 range since fewer experiments were conducted there. This diagram is the outcome of the model during the operation of the system, and operators can view this dashboard during water treatment as a monitoring tool to anticipate changes. The distribution highlights which pH and mass combinations are associated with higher or lower removal, enabling a better understanding of optimal conditions. The color gradient and

symbol size convey differences in removal performance, which is useful for refining process parameters. With the application of the KF concept, a dynamic model is presented to smarten the model. In fact, according to the unknown data in the operation concept, CSVLoader is connected to the application programming interface of telecommunication in the sensor network of water treatment plants, then the performance is predicted by the algorithm, and finally, according to undesirable performances of the heavy metal ions treatment, alarms will be informed to operators. For example, according to Fig. 6(d) is the output of the model. Considering Fig. 6(d), it can be found that the RP is categorized and the light and stronger blue colors are alarm zones for operators which they can be informed by some telecommunication protocols such as email or short message service (Ataei et al., 2024).

In the mentioned modeling, the experimental data is applied from experiments. The data is based on experiments, and in real water treatment processes, similar data could be provided in real time by sensors measuring parameters such as pH, IC, mass of adsorbent, and time. The RP of heavy metal adsorption can then be predicted using machine learning computations. The entire process can be implemented on processors such as Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), and others. Technologies in this field include Xylem's Decision Intelligence Platform (DIP) (Xylem US, 2025), Siemens' MindSphere IoT Platform for Water (Siemens Global, 2025), and ABB's Ability™ Smart Sensor Technology (ABB Group, 2025).

According to the earlier KF design and basic modeling workflow, the development of the expert system was further advanced in a programmable environment to enable dynamic prediction and automated decision-making. Since the TRF method displayed greater accuracy and robustness during the initial MLA screening, the continuation of modeling was centered on TRF as the fundamental prediction engine. In the next phase, the adsorption performance values (RP) were categorized into four operating classes: [11 %–33 %], [33 %–55 %], [55 %–77 %], and [77 %–99 %], to enable multi-level categorization for process monitoring. Subsequently, key TRF hyperparameters (number of trees, minimum leaf size, and maximum splits) were tuned to optimize model performance. Finally, the dynamically optimized model was integrated into an alarm management system that flags operational risk conditions

using the threshold $RP < 80\%$, forming the basis of a real-time smart control module.

Fig. 7(a) showing the impact of the number of trees on predictive performance for the TRF model: with increasing number of trees (10–100), R^2 increases sharply and RMSE decreases, meaning better generalization; but after 100, both metrics start to slow down in changes indicating progressively smaller gains in accuracy and finally suggesting that circa hundred is a good compromise between accuracy and cost. The influence of the minimum leaf size on model performance shown in Fig. 7(b), the model is best in terms of R^2 and RMSE when a small leaf size (1–5) is used owing to the fact that the fine-grained decision regions can capture nonlinear adsorption regimes, and large leaf sizes result in fast performance degradation with low R^2 but high RMSE because of too simple tree structures, assigned because 1 is preferable for description of complex interplay governing LDC-mediated adsorptive behaviors. Similarly, Fig. 7(c) highlights the sensitivity of the TRF model to the number of maximum splits, where R^2 fluctuates across the evaluated range but reaches its peak near 75 splits with a corresponding minimum in RMSE; values significantly above or below this threshold compromise predictive stability through underfitting or overfitting, indicating that moderate tree depth is ideal for representing the combined effects of pH, metal type, initial concentration, adsorbent mass, and contact time.

Fig. 7(d) summarizes the model's classification performance over four RP categories after hyperparameter adjustment and for test results. The confusion matrix demonstrates great accuracy for the top classes [55 %–77 %] and [77 %–99 %], which dominate the dataset and correlate to consistent adsorption circumstances. Misclassifications primarily occur in the lower classes, where fewer samples and overlapping adsorption patterns impede separability. However, the model consistently detects operational states with high efficiency, which is essential for intelligent process monitoring. Model accuracy for continuous RP prediction is further proven in Fig. 7(e) for the training dataset. TRF successfully captures the nonlinear relationships regulating heavy metal adsorption, as evidenced by the close clustering of points around the perfect-fit line ($R^2 = 0.9242$). This demonstrates the superiority of TRF over linear models, which lack the flexibility to reflect

Fig. 7. TRF sensitivity and performance: (a) optimal tree count (=100); (b) best accuracy at leaf size = 1; (c) optimal splits = 75; (d) RP-class confusion matrix; (e) train R^2 ; (f) RP distribution with 80 % alarm threshold; (g) test R^2 ; (h) improved R^2 after tuning; (i) time-RP trends with alarm detection in low-performance.

multivariable interactions in CDW-derived adsorbents. Comparable performance is shown in the test dataset (Fig. 7g), where an R^2 of 0.9037 shows high generalization and low overfitting. The RMSE of around 6.69 is suitable for real-time environmental applications, where continual variations in input parameters are expected. In the following, The distribution of expected RP values in relation to the 80 % alert level is shown in Fig. 7(f) to facilitate real-time decision-making. The program properly recognizes a fraction of circumstances where RP falls below 80 %, delivering proactive alerts and relevant changes. This threshold-based approach is the foundation of the alert management module of the expert system.

The optimized TRF model outperforms the baseline configuration for both training and test sets in Fig. 7(h), which provides additional validity of the optimization technique. The diminishing gap between train and test R^2 values shows better generalization and reduced variance, illustrating the necessity of regular hyperparameter adjustment for preserving stability in real-time deployments. Lastly, a dynamic representation of RP performance over time for various metal ions is shown in Fig. 7(i). While Mn^{2+} shows more fluctuation and more frequent excursions into suboptimal regions, Pb^{2+} continuously stays above the 80 % threshold, indicating its significant affinity for LDC. These temporal patterns, together with metal-specific behavior, indicate the strength of the expert system in recording real-time aberrations and generating warnings when RP decreases below operational expectations. Collectively, Fig. 7(a-i) demonstrates that hyperparameter adjustment greatly boosts TRF prediction performance and stability, while the four-class RP categorization supports operational decision-making. The alarm subsystem accurately identifies instances where $RP < 80\%$, providing timely intelligence for intervention. Altogether, the integrated expert system indicates tremendous promise for real-time monitoring and automated control in Industry 4.0-oriented water treatment applications.

According to Fig. 8, for large-scale implementation of the presented smart control system, the soft-sensor system is built into a three-tier architecture consisting of the physical sensing layer, the edge-computing and data-integration layer (TRF model), and the cloud-based decision and control layer (alarm system). In the sensing layer, online instruments including pH probes (Uppuluri et al., 2023),

flow-based adsorbent-dosing controls (Besenhard et al., 2017; Dosing pump), reaction-time meters, and heavy metal concentration analyzers (Voda instrum; Zou et al., 2009), continuously send real-time data. These devices interact through conventional industrial protocols such as Modbus-Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) (Pricop et al., 2017), 4-20 mA analog signal (Dominguez-Nicolas et al., 2012)/Recommended Standard (RS)-485 (Lv and Wang, 2010), or Open Platform Communications-Unified Architecture (OPC-UA) (Vimos and Sacoto Cabrera, 2018), ensuring interoperability among varied treatment units. The captured signals are transmitted into the edge layer where a dedicated industrial gateway or microcontroller (e.g., advanced reduced instruction set computer machine: ARM-based unit) (Rahman et al., 2024) performs initial filtering, timestamp synchronization, and formatting.

These pre-processed data are subsequently transferred to the computational hardware either a local server or cloud platform, using secure Message Queuing Telemetry Transport/HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure (MQTT/HTTPS) protocols (Colitti et al., 2011; Hunkeler et al., 2008). The TRF-based soft-sensor accepts structured feature inputs (pH, adsorbent mass, heavy metal type and concentration, and contact time) and conducts continuous prediction of RP while simultaneously evaluating alert thresholds ($RP < 80\%$). When sub-optimal performance is observed, the system delivers control recommendations to the dosing pump and reactor controller, and simultaneously receives RSM-optimized values for pH and adsorbent mass for corrective action. All data streams, prediction outputs, and control actions are logged in a uniform dataset for periodic model retraining. This modular communication architecture facilitates the large-scale Industry 4.0 implementation of intelligent adsorption-based water treatment and enables smooth connection with current Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) (Ahmad Zaki Hamidi et al., 2018) systems.

The application of expert systems in the adsorption process as a DSS is rare (Krzywanski et al., 2024). While, in the following, some different DSS in water/wastewater processes is discussed.

The DSS in this study, utilizing WEKA/MATLAB for machine learning and the Knowledge Flow platform for decision-making, handles data through descriptive statistics, RSM for sensitivity analysis, and MLAs for predictions. It controls parameters such as pH, IC, adsorbent mass, and

Fig. 8. Conceptual model of the smart control system for heavy metal adsorption based on the MLA-RSM framework developed in this study.

time, with removal percentages as outputs. In contrast, the expert system by Puñal et al. (2002) employs Visual Basic, Access, and MATLAB for software integration, focusing on real-time monitoring and fault diagnosis in anaerobic wastewater treatment, managing variables like gas flow, pH, and temperature to predict system states and provide operator recommendations.

In this study, the DSS uses descriptive statistics, RSM, and MLAs for predictions, controlling parameters like pH, IC, adsorbent mass, and time, with removal percentages as outputs. In contrast, Krzywanski et al. (2024)'s study develops an AI-based Diagnostic (AID) system using an AutoMLAs approach for adsorption cooling and desalination systems. They employed the DataRobot platform to select the best predictive model from 42 different models, focusing on 42 input parameters. The AID system achieved high efficiency, with an Area Under the Curve (AUC) of 0.988, RMSE of 0.2, and LogLoss of 0.14, and accurately predicted system health and failure states. While this study focuses on heavy metal adsorption with specific optimization, Krzywanski et al. (2024)'s work emphasizes predictive maintenance in cooling and desalination, showcasing broader applications and higher prediction accuracy. Hu et al. (2017) demonstrated a sensor-free electrothermal swing adsorption system using Activated Carbon Fiber Cloth (ACFC), controlled via electrical resistance changes. While innovative, the study relied on fundamental simulation rather than machine learning, limiting real-time implementation feasibility. Mursic et al. (1996) used a LABVIEW-based interface to precisely operate an automated adsorption isotherm equipment. Nevertheless, the system lacks adaptability for real-time decision support system applications and is based on basic simulation rather than machine learning.

4. Conclusion

Adsorption is considered a suitable method for high concentration wastewater treatment, especially for heavy metals, yet its efficiency and automation require further improvement for industrial applications. This study focuses on optimizing the parameters for removing Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} from water using LDC waste as an adsorbent by applying RSM. Based on the experimental data and RSM optimization, pH was found to be the main factor, with the optimum occurring close to pH 5, which is the greatest practical value without precipitation danger, even though the overall best conditions depend on the combined impacts of all variables. For Pb^{2+} , pH 5, 0.13 g of adsorbent, 33.5 min of contact time, and a starting concentration of 35 mg L^{-1} were the ideal conditions. The ideal parameters for Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} were pH 5, 0.15 g of adsorbent, starting concentrations of 10 mg L^{-1} , and contact periods of 110 and 120 min, respectively. The optimal conditions for each metal within the examined operational range is defined by these combined parameters. Furthermore, adsorbent mass and contact time also influence removal efficiency, though their effects are metal-specific. In this stage of the study, it is shown that of the twenty different algorithms tested, TRF and FMLP, along with the lazy IBK, were the most accurate for predicting RP during the adsorption process. Adjusting these algorithms shows the TRF algorithm works best at an 80 % split percentage, as indicated by a CC of ~ 0.99 . Finally, a DSS with KF concepts is developed to manage and control alarm settings for heavy metal contamination removal in water treatment facilities. The DSS based on the TRF model in WEKA's KF platform predicted Pb^{2+} removal efficiency and provided real-time alerts for RP values below 80 %. These alerts, using automated thresholds and data mining, were set for smart control, enabling automated operational control in smart water treatment systems. As well, using real-time data, the DSS was capable of predicting in a range of 30-100 % heavy metal decontamination efficiency.

To forecast adsorption capacity, model kinetics, and enable real-time decision-making, future research should employ advanced machine learning models with continuous sensor-based data. Techniques such as deep forest models, neural networks, and XGBoost can enhance screening, mechanism interpretation, and optimization. Additionally,

integrating metaheuristic approaches like NSGA-II with machine learning may further improve performance and reduce prediction errors. This study is limited by the inherent variability of waste-derived adsorbents, which affects consistency. Algorithm performance should also be validated in real water treatment plants with plug-flow conditions, and larger real-world datasets are needed to strengthen reliability and accuracy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohammad Gheibi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Seyyed Roohollah Masoomi:** Writing – original draft, Software, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Eftekhari:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martin Paluśák:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization. **Daniele Silvestri:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Černík:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Stanisław Waclawek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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